

Kinetics of Silver (I)-Catalysed Oxidation of Indigo Carmine by Potassium Peroxydisulphate—Catalytic Kinetic Determination of Micro Amounts of Silver

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The kinetics of oxidation of indigo carmine by peroxydisulphate catalysed by silver (I) was investigated. The reaction is of first order with respect to peroxydisulphate and silver (I) and zero order in indigo carmine. Increase of ionic strength decreases the rate. The reaction mixture initiates vinyl polymerization. Activation parameters were calculated. The catalysed reaction was utilized for developing kinetic method for the determination of Ag (I) in micro gram concentrations (in the range 0.3–4.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) with an average error of 2%. The standard deviation, coefficient of variation and percentage error were also calculated.

THE kinetics of peroxydisulphate oxidation of a number of organic and inorganic substrates have been reported and reviewed^{1,2}. The kinetics of the uncatalysed oxidation of indigo carmine by peroxydisulphate was studied by Subba Rao *et al*³. Kaufmann⁴ has investigated the kinetics of the oxidation of indigo carmine by peroxydisulphate using benzene, petroleum ether etc., as sensitizers and Fe(II) as catalyst. However, the kinetics of silver(I)-catalysed oxidation of indigo carmine by peroxydisulphate has not been studied so far. Hence the present authors have taken up a kinetic study of this catalysis and their results are reported in this paper. The authors have pressed this catalysis into use for developing a sensitive method for the kinetic determination of silver(I) in microgram amounts.

Experimental

All the materials used were of analytical reagent grade. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the optical density of the unreacted indigo carmine at 610 nm. At this wavelength indigo carmine has maximum absorption and obeys Beer's law in the range of indigo carmine concentrations employed. All the other materials concerned have negligible absorption at this wavelength.

Stoichiometry: It was found that one mole of indigo carmine consumed two moles of peroxydisulphate; isatin monosulphonic acid is the product of oxidation.

All the kinetic runs were carried out keeping the concentration of peroxydisulphate in excess (at least ten times) over that of indigo carmine. Plots of optical density versus time, were straight lines (Fig 1). This shows that the reaction obeys zero order kinetics with respect to indigo carmine. The pseudo zero order rate constants, k_0 , were calculated from the slopes of the straight lines. The plot of pseudo zero order rate

Fig. 1. Plots of Optical Density versus time
[Indigo-Carmine] = $2.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{M}$; $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$
= $4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$;
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.01 \text{M}$; $\mu = 0.08$; Temp = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$
 $[\text{Ag}^+] \times 10^3, \text{M} = \text{O}-\text{O}-\text{O}$ 2.38, $\bullet-\bullet-\bullet$ 4.75,
 $\Delta-\Delta-\Delta$ 7.13, $\square-\square-\square$ 9.50, $\times-\times-\times$ 11.88.

constant, k_0 , versus concentration of peroxydisulphate was found to be straight line passing through the origin showing that the reaction obeys first order kinetics with respect to peroxydisulphate (Fig. 2). The plot of k_0 versus concentration of Ag(I) was also found to be a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 3). This shows the direct dependence of rate on silver(I) concentration and the extent of uncatalysed reaction is negligibly small under these experimental conditions. The initial rates were also determined for different initial concentrations of the indigo carmine keeping the concentrations of all the materials constant using the method described by Laidler⁵. The data are presented

Fig. 2. Plot of k_0 versus $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$
 [Indigo Carmine] = $2.17 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[Ag^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$;
 $[H_2SO_4] = 0.01 M$; $\mu = 0.08$; Temp = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

Fig. 3. Plot of k_0 versus $[Ag^+]$
 [Indigo Carmine] = $2.17 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$;
 $[H_2SO_4] = 0.01 M$; $\mu = 0.08$; Temp = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

in Table 1. It is evident from the data, that the rate of the reaction is independent of the concentration of the indigo carmine, showing the zero order kinetics with respect to indigo carmine. Moreover, the initial rate of the catalysed reaction was found to be 2.36×10^{-7} moles, litre $^{-1}$, min $^{-1}$ at $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, [indigo carmine] = $2.17 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $[Ag(I)] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; whereas the initial rate of the uncatalysed reaction under identical conditions was found to be 6.0×10^{-9} moles, litre $^{-1}$, min $^{-1}$. It was

also observed that the rate of the reaction was not appreciably altered by change in acid concentration (Table 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF THE CONCENTRATION OF INDIGO CARMINE AND ACRYLONITRILE ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF INDIGO CARMINE BY PEROXYDISULPHATE.

$$[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} M, [Ag^+] = 7.13 \times 10^{-3} M, [H_2SO_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$$

$$\mu = 0.08, \text{ Temperature} = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$$

[Indigo Carmine] $\times 10^5 M$	[Acrylonitrile] M	$k_0 \times 10^7$ moles. litre $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$
1.62	—	16.43
2.17	—	16.33
2.71	—	16.33
3.25	—	16.20
2.17	0.6	11.06
2.17	0.9	8.81
2.17	1.2	6.45

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF THE CONCENTRATION OF ACID AND IONIC STRENGTH ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF INDIGO CARMINE BY PEROXYDISULPHATE.

$$[\text{Indigo Carmine}] = 2.17 \times 10^{-5} M, [S_2O_8^{2-}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} M, [Ag^+] = 4.75 \times 10^{-3} M, \text{ Temperature} = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ$$

$[H_2SO_4] \times 10^3 M$	μ	$k_0 \times 10^7$ moles. litre $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$
2.0	0.08	10.85
4.0	0.08	10.76
6.0	0.08	10.96
8.0	0.08	11.00
10.0	0.08	10.96
10.0	0.06	13.43
10.0	0.04	16.43

The reaction was studied at different ionic strengths by varying the concentration of sodium perchlorate. The increase in ionic strength resulted in decrease in the rate of the reaction. The data were presented in Table 2. A plot of $\log k_0$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ was a straight line with a negative slope of 2.1. This shows that the rate determining step involves positive and negative ions, the product of the charges being -2 .

Effect of Acrylonitrile: The reaction mixture with acrylonitrile yielded a white precipitate showing that the reaction initiates vinyl polymerization. Further, the rate measurements before the solid polymer formation have shown that an increase in acrylonitrile concentration reduced the rate of the oxidation of indigo carmine (Table 1). The result indicates that the reaction involves a radical mechanism.

Activation Parameters : The values of k_0 were determined at four temperatures. A plot of $\log k_0$ versus $1/T$ was a straight line. From the slope of this straight line, the activation energy was calculated to be 12.0 ± 0.2 K.Cal.mole⁻¹ which is much less than the reported value of the activation energy of the uncatalysed reaction³ (17.4 ± 0.2 K.cal.mole⁻¹). This shows that the catalyst decreases the activation energy of the reaction. The data, further, yielded value -30 ± 1 e.u. for ΔS^\ddagger . From the above results the observed rate law may be given as

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Indigo carmine}] = k[S_2O_8^{2-}][Ag^+]$$

A similar kinetic pattern was observed for a number of Ag^+ -catalysed oxidations by peroxydisulphate⁶⁻¹³ and a chain mechanism has been proposed in each case. Hence the authors believe that the present reaction also proceeds through a chain mechanism.

Determination of Silver (I) : In order to determine the concentrations of the catalyst, neither variable time procedure nor fixed time procedure can be employed^{14,15}. From the results of kinetic study it was found that the rate of the reaction is independent of acid concentration in the range $(2-10) \times 10^{-3} M$; but the rate increased with increase in temperature and decreased with increase in ionic strength in the range $(4-8) \times 10^{-2}$. Hence for convenience pseudo zero order rate constants were determined for all the runs at a temperature of 30° , at an acid concentration of $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and at constant ionic strength of 5.5×10^{-2} .

Recommended Procedure : The authors recommend the following procedure for determining silver (I) in microgram level. Calculated amounts of indigo carmine and sulphuric acid to give overall concentrations of $1.88 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively are mixed with known concentrations of silver nitrate and water is added to give an overall volume of 100 ml. The reaction mixture is kept in a thermostat at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Potassium peroxydisulphate was also placed in the same thermostat. After equilibrium is attained calculated quantity of peroxydisulphate to give an overall concentration of $1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$ is added to the reaction mixture simultaneously starting the stop watch. The course of the reaction is followed by measuring the optical density of the unreacted indigo carmine at 610 nm at suitable intervals of time using Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. The pseudo zero order rate constant k_0 is determined from the optical density-time plot.

Construction of the Calibration Curve : The values of k_0 were determined at different concentrations of silver (I) which were 30-400 times less than those employed in the investigation of effect of silver (I) concentration on k_0 in the kinetic study. This was done with a view to develop a method for the determination of silver (I) in microgram quantities. A plot of k_0 versus concentration of silver (I) was found to be a good straight line (Fig. 4), with an intercept on k_0 axis, which gives the rate of uncatalysed reaction. The observance of intercept is presumably due to much

Fig. 4. Calibration Curve
 [Indigo Carmine] = $1.88 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$;
 $[H_2SO_4] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 0.055$; $Temp = 30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

lower concentrations of silver (I) employed. By the method of least squares, the following equation of the straight line was obtained with a correlation coefficient of 0.99 :

$$Ag^+ = 6.9842 \times 10^6 k_0 - 3.4022$$

Unknown amounts of silver (I) were calculated using this equation. The standard deviation, coefficient of

TABLE 3 - REPRODUCIBILITY OF A KINETIC MICRO DETERMINATION OF Ag^+ .

[Indigo Carmine] = $1.88 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.4 \times 10^{-2} M$,
 $[H_2SO_4] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\mu = 0.055$, Temperature = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$

Ag ⁺ taken μg/ml	Ag ⁺ found ± S.D μg/ml	No. of analysis	Coefficient of variation	% Error
0.34	0.32 ± 0.02	4	5.5	-4.9
1.02	1.00 ± 0.04	6	4.1	-2.1
1.70	1.68 ± 0.03	6	1.8	-1.0
2.38	2.30 ± 0.05	6	2.3	-3.3
3.06	3.07 ± 0.04	6	1.3	+0.2
3.74	3.69 ± 0.05	6	1.3	-1.5

variation and percentage error for each of the determinations were calculated and the results were presented in Table 3. The ions such as Na^+ , K^+ , CH_3COO^- ,

ClO_4^- did not interfere even when they are present in 100 fold amounts to that of Ag^+ . The ions Al^{3+} , NH_4^+ , Cd^{2+} , Th^{4+} , Mg^{2+} , Li^+ , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Be^{2+} did not interfere even though they are present in twice the amount of Ag^+ . The ions Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} which catalyse the reaction between peroxydisulphate and indigo carmine did not affect the rate when their concentration ratio to that of Ag^+ is 0.001 and 0.06 respectively.

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